

8T – Indexed Hamiltonians

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will present an idea regarding the Hamiltonian of the 8T theory. The Hamiltonian is now expanded to include the kinetic energy of all manifolds, and same for the potential energy, which is the summation of all arbitrary variations over the spectra of the packet.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

The Hamilton idea could be presented in a rather simple way assuming we accept the notion of the multiverse as true, which is the case according to the 8T main equation in universe packet representation (2.1.A) and (2.1.B). In classical physics, the Hamilton is classified as summation of two terms, potential and kinetic. However, in the 8T it is the summation of two indexed terms, which indicate we have to sum over the kinetic and potential energies of all accelerating manifolds in the packet. That is in classical and Quantum mechanics:

$$\hat{H} = \hat{T} + \hat{U}$$

So in the 8T the Hamiltonian must be varied to represent the idea of distinct manifolds which composing the packet. For that purpose, the author will present an arrow and a morphism:

$$\mathcal{G}: \hat{T} \rightarrow \hat{T}_i$$

$$\hat{T}_i = \frac{\partial^2 g'_i}{\partial t^2}; \forall s_{1 \rightarrow n}$$

For the potential energy, i.e. matter operator, the author will use the arbitrary variation term which vanish into zero, i.e. (1.48) over all the manifolds in the packet.

$$\sigma: \hat{U} \rightarrow \hat{U}_i$$

$$\hat{U}_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i; \forall s_{1 \rightarrow n}$$

That is by **no means** an indication that the potential energy is zero, but rather that the potential energy has no curvature, i.e. that matter pairs in a way that does not allow curvature to manifest itself, but it's still exist in a form of Quarks and the reason Quarks can not escape, to ensure the manifold stationarity condition. The new Hamiltonian is a summation of two indexed terms; each represents the kinetic energy of the manifold, and the potential energy of the manifold with a unique index and a unique arrow. The idea of indexed Hamiltonian is a result of the features of the 8T, acceleration outward from extremum curvatures, flatness, arbitrary variations vanishing into matter and manifold packets. This idea is clearly indicating that in order to understand one universe, it can only be done by analyzing the packet of universes itself.

$$\hat{H} = \hat{T}_i + \hat{U}_i \tag{1.5}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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